

Real and synthetic scenarios generated for the development, training, virtual testing and validation of CCAM systems

SYNERGIES

D2.1 Stakeholder high-level requirements

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents a comprehensive analysis of stakeholder needs and high-level requirements for the SYNERGIES project, which aims to enhance the development and validation of Cooperative, Connected, and Automated Mobility (CCAM) systems through a unified approach to scenario-based testing.

The primary objective of SYNERGIES is to establish a federated European scenario dataspace, providing unified access to various existing scenario databases. This approach, building upon the work done in the SUNRISE project, allows users to interact with multiple, inhomogeneous scenario databases as if they were a single, cohesive repository. SYNERGIES aim to facilitate seamless access to the available databases and the integration of existing resources.

Key aspects covered in this document include:

1. **Unified Access to European Scenario Dataspace:** SYNERGIES will develop a federated layer that enables users to access and utilize scenarios from multiple databases across Europe, enhancing collaboration and resource sharing in the CCAM ecosystem.
2. **Expansion of Scenario Coverage:** The project will extend the range of relevant scenarios by providing a new set covering rural and urban environments, enabling complex situation descriptions. This will address gaps in existing databases and improve the comprehensiveness of available scenarios.
3. **AI-Powered Data Processing Tools:** SYNERGIES will develop (semi)automatic AI data processing tools for efficient scenario extraction, enhancing the ability to generate and analyze relevant scenarios from diverse data sources.
4. **Establishment of a Marketplace:** The project will create a marketplace to facilitate accessibility to the toolset for future scenario generation, promoting innovation and collaboration among stakeholders.
5. **Needs Assessment:** A detailed analysis of the requirements expressed by each stakeholder group, providing a comprehensive understanding of the expectations for the SYNERGIES federated dataspace and associated tools.
6. **High-Level Requirements:** A structured list of requirements derived from stakeholder inputs, encompassing the expected functionalities of the federated dataspace, performance criteria, and conditions of use.

This deliverable serves as a critical foundation for aligning the project's technical development with the expectations of various stakeholders in the CCAM ecosystem. It is an essential output of Task 2.1 and will guide subsequent tasks within Work Package 2, ensuring that the SYNERGIES federated dataspace and associated tools meet the needs of the entire CCAM community.

1 INTRODUCTION

The automotive industry is undergoing a significant transformation with the arrival of Connected, Cooperative, and Automated Mobility (CCAM) systems. As these technologies advance, there is an increasing need for comprehensive and standardized methods to develop, test, and validate these systems to ensure their safety and reliability. The SYNERGIES project emerges as a response to this need, aiming to create a unified platform for scenario-based testing and validation of CCAM systems.

CCAM technologies promise to revolutionize transportation by enhancing road safety, improving traffic efficiency, and reducing environmental impact. However, the complexity of these systems, coupled with the vast array of potential driving scenarios they must navigate, presents significant challenges in their development and validation. Traditional testing methods are often insufficient to cover the multitude of scenarios that automated vehicles might encounter in real-world conditions.

The SYNERGIES project addresses these challenges by creating a comprehensive platform that includes:

1. **A Scenario Dataspace:** A centralized repository of diverse driving scenarios, ranging from common situations to edge cases, providing a rich dataset for testing and validation.
2. **A Marketplace of Tools:** A platform offering various tools and methodologies for scenario generation, testing, and analysis, enabling stakeholders to access and contribute to state-of-the-art resources.
3. **Interoperability Framework:** A system that ensures compatibility and data exchange between different tools, databases, and stakeholders, fostering collaboration and standardization across the industry.

The project brings together a diverse group of stakeholders, including Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs), Tier X suppliers, researchers, infrastructure data providers, regulatory bodies, and technical services. By consolidating their expertise and requirements, SYNERGIES aims to create a platform that addresses the needs of the entire CCAM ecosystem.

This document outlines the high-level requirements gathered from these stakeholders, providing a foundation for the development of the SYNERGIES platform. It captures the diverse needs and expectations of each stakeholder group, ensuring that the final platform will be comprehensive, user-friendly, and aligned with industry standards and regulatory requirements.

As the automotive industry continues to evolve towards higher levels of automation, the SYNERGIES project plays a crucial role in establishing a common ground for CCAM validation. By facilitating collaboration, standardization, and innovation, the project aims to accelerate the safe deployment of automated driving technologies, ultimately contributing to the realization of safer, more efficient, and sustainable transportation systems.

2 STAKEHOLDER NEEDS

2.1 OEMs

2.1.1 Context

Scenarios are used by OEMs in the complete process from the design of ADAS and ADS, verification and validation, up to the homologation of ADS, e.g., according to UN R157 on ALKS, motorway Chauffeur (SAE Level 3 AD system) and EU R2022/1426 on SAE Level 4 AD Systems. Scenarios are used in several domains to describe the use cases to define the customer performances (system dynamic behaviour at vehicle level or HMI level), to describe the use cases of the system engineering methodology, and to describe the “critical” use cases of the safety demonstration including the ones from safety analysis and the ones’ from accidentology. To cover these needs, scenarios are coming from different sources, such as accident or incident analysis, real world driving, and safety analysis. Since Stuttgart Automated Vehicle Symposium in 2018, it is clear for OEMs and Tiers that it is not anymore possible to work alone on such a topic, so huge is the task. In this context, for example, an OEM wants to provide collected fleet data to partners and consume data from other partners. From the collected data, an OEM wants to create, exchange and use test scenarios. Ultimately, an OEM wants to validate its ADAS/AD functions on a scenario data space.

For this purpose, an OEM wants to use a common platform to exchange data and scenarios between partners in a common scenario data space, in a common format, driving data and scenarios coming from different sources, coming from and to be used by different entities, like HMI department, Safety department, Testing department, Accidentology Laboratory, Technical Service, OEM, Tier1s, AI suppliers, Ministry of Transport.

Moreover, for SAE level 4 systems, in Europe, the homologation of the ADS is not enough to allow the usage on roads of these systems. They shall be included in an overarching system. Over the usage of scenarios for “ADS” development, scenarios are also used for Automated Road Transport Systems (ARTS) development exactly in the same manner but not on the same perimeter. Requirements to comply with are not defined by UN or EU regulations but by national or local laws, and a lot of new stakeholders are involved: transport operators, audit companies, local authorities in charge of transport, first responders, etc.

To conclude, as an optimum, the SYNERGIES scenario data space should be the basis for ADS and ADAS design and safety demonstration, for ADS homologation, for ARTS in service authorization across Europe, for the Automotive and Mobility industry, and for “in use monitoring & reporting” that includes sharing scenarios discovered “in use”.

2.1.2 Stakeholder needs

An OEM uses scenario-based testing for development and validation of ADAS/AD and subsequently for homologation purposes in Europe. In this context, an OEM wants to **provide collected fleet data to partners and consume data from other partners**. For this purpose, an OEM wants to **use a common platform to exchange data between partners**. This platform should provide *Data Security and Privacy* where needed, e.g. by implementing measures for *User Access and Permissions*. To serve the variety of potential use cases for the data, (e.g. data centers, proving grounds, etc.), these concepts should be extended for *Offline and Disconnected Operations*. As the platform will interface a variety of other systems, it should support *Interoperability and Compatibility*. In order to achieve that goal, a list of *Required Standards* should

be developed based on the project use-cases. This list should result in a *SYNERGIES Relevant Standards Whitepaper*. For this dedicated topic, *Further Information on the Standards* should be provided to support platform developers and users. Thinking one step ahead, *Contribution to Standards* that can evolve as feedback from the platform development can help to improve the former. *Scalability and Performance* and *Extensibility and Modularity* are key enablers for such implementations and form the basis for sustainable development.

Based on this platform, an OEM wants to use and contribute to a common scenario data set with partners. From the collected data, an OEM wants to **create, exchange and use scenarios**. Besides collection of data from fleet data, the platform should be capable of handling other data sources, such as *In-Service Monitoring and Reporting (ISMR) Scenarios*. It should further support consistent processing of the scenarios, which should involve *Detection of Similar Scenarios*. For this purpose, *Standardized Data Formats and Interfaces* should be supported by the platform. This is especially true for *Consistent Interfaces for Data Recording* and a *Standardized, Established Output Format*, namely the *Scenario Export Format*. Nevertheless, to support all users and partners, *Proprietary Formats and Interfaces* should be supported, as well. This can incorporate the export of *Additional Scenario Export Formats*. For both cases, representativeness and relevance of the data should be assured by appropriate measures for *Versioning and Change Management* and *Reporting and Analytics to enable Traceability, Version Control, and Access Management of the Scenario Database*.

Ultimately, an OEM wants to **validate its ADAS/AD functions on a scenario data space**. As an optimum, the scenario data space in the SYNERGIES database is the basis for homologation across Europe. This requires that the SYNERGIES scenario dataspace provides a *Representation of a Scenario Space Designed for Homologation Use-Cases*. This scenario space should contain an *Interoperable Scenario Database Development*. Acceptance for the corresponding scope, methodology and processes should be achieved in close collaboration with regulators, e.g. by *Harmonization of Scenario-Based Safety Assessments Across Borders and Jurisdictions*. In any case, it requires comprehensive *Documentation and Support* as well as *Community Engagement and Collaboration*. Finally, the acceptance as basis for homologation, can require suitable *Open-Source or Open-Access Licenses* for the corresponding scenarios and required tooling.

2.1.3 Use Case Diagram

“Scenario-based testing for development and validation of ADAS/AD”

An OEM uses scenario-based testing for development and validation of ADAS/AD and subsequently for homologation purposes in Europe. In this context, an OEM wants to **provide collected fleet data to partners and consume data from other partners**. For this purpose, an OEM wants to **use a common platform to exchange data between partners**. Based on this platform, an OEM wants to use and contribute to a common scenario data set with partners. From the collected data, an OEM wants to **create, exchange and use scenarios**. Ultimately, an OEM wants to **validate its ADAS/AD functions on a scenario data space**. As an optimum, the scenario data space in the SYNERGIES database is the basis for homologation across Europe.

Figure 1 OEM Use Case diagram

2.2 TierXs

2.2.1 Context

Having a large amount of data, especially scenario-based data, is crucial for the development and validation of automated driving systems for several reasons:

1. **Comprehensive Training:** Automated driving systems rely on machine learning algorithms that need to be trained on diverse datasets. A large volume of data ensures that these systems can learn from a wide range of driving scenarios, including rare and complex situations, which improves their overall performance and reliability.
2. **Scenario Diversity:** Scenario-based data includes various driving conditions, such as different weather, traffic patterns, road types, and unexpected events. This diversity helps in creating robust algorithms that can handle real-world complexities and ensure safe and efficient driving.
3. **Edge Case Handling:** Edge cases are rare but critical situations that automated driving systems must be able to handle. Having extensive scenario-based data allows developers to identify and address these edge cases during the development phase, reducing the risk of failures in real-world applications.
4. **Regulatory Compliance:** Regulatory bodies require extensive testing and validation to certify automated driving systems. A robust dataset helps in meeting these regulatory requirements by providing evidence of the system's safety and reliability.
5. **Continuous Improvement:** Automated driving systems need to evolve and improve over time. Access to a large and diverse dataset allows for continuous learning and refinement of algorithms, leading to better performance and adaptation to new driving environments.
6. **User Trust:** Demonstrating that an automated driving system has been tested and validated with extensive scenario-based data helps build user trust. Users are more likely to adopt and rely on these systems if they are confident in their safety and reliability.

So, in the rapidly evolving field of automated and connected vehicles, it is essential for Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs), Tier 1 suppliers, and all stakeholders to collaborate closely in the generation and usage of data for development and validation.

Beyond the cost reduction and validation acceleration effect, the Tier1 are interested to be a driving force in the communalization of the process, scenario, data and tools in order to:

1. Converge to a standard format for data and validation process. This can ensure consistency and interoperability intra and inter systems.
2. Accelerate the innovation with on the shelves data that can be used in a quick loop of prototyping to be able to maintain a competitive edge.

Some CCAM operational domain are already mature, and the specification requests are well identified in the industry in general as in partial automaton like LKS, ACC or in total automation in specific time like the automated parking for example.

Level 3 or Level 4 automation are introducing new concepts and requirements that still under definition. The coverage of all use cases in the homologation process for example is not realistic and there is a need to define which subset is mandatory and which one is possible to be applied as a subset randomly for example.

2.2.2 Stakeholder needs

While collaboration in validation database sharing for automated driving systems offers many benefits, there are also several limitations and challenges to consider:

1. **Data Privacy and Security:** Sharing large amounts of data between different stakeholders raises concerns about data privacy and security. Ensuring that sensitive information is protected and that data sharing complies with privacy regulations is a significant challenge. A different level of security and different cercle of privacy can be added for example to enhance the sharing experience.
2. **Intellectual Property :** Companies may be reluctant to share data that they consider proprietary or that gives them a competitive edge. Th e clarification of IP and the limit of the usage of data can be also an enabler for this function.
3. **Standardization Issues:** having the standard validation in-line with the data offers is ensuring the convergence to a common usage and sharing of the data.
4. **Quality and Consistency:** Ensuring the quality and consistency of shared data and the ground truth are crucial for effective validation. Even if the quality is difficult to harmonize between different entity but the transparency on the condition of data recording can be helpful to define the limit of the usage of these data.
5. **Regulatory and Legal Barriers:** Different regions may have varying regulations and legal requirements for data sharing, which can complicate collaboration efforts. Navigating these regulatory landscapes requires careful planning and compliance.

The limit of the collaboration in the field of data base and validation process are coming from the diversity of the sensors specification and the variety of the sensors combination. The representability of sensor combination is very important to assess the performance on a robotaxi for example.

The responsibility of the targeted platform is crucial to build a trustful common place in which more collaboration between the different stakeholders is fluid and successful.

2.2.3 Use Case Diagram

Figure 2 TierXs Use Case diagram

2.3 Infrastructure-data provider

2.3.1 Context

Infrastructure-data providers supply accurate, high-resolution trajectory data, captured through roadside sensors and monitoring systems, which are foundational to the validation and performance of Connected, Cooperative, and Automated Mobility (CCAM) systems. These data, consisting of detailed vehicle movement patterns and interactions, enable the creation of realistic scenarios that accurately reflect the behaviour of traffic in various environments.

The SYNERGIES project enables the trajectory data of infrastructure-data providers to be integrated into interoperable scenario databases, accessible by stakeholders such as OEMs, regulatory bodies, and testing facilities. Their interest is driven by several key factors:

1. **Data Utilization and Reach.** By contributing to the project, infrastructure-data providers can ensure their datasets are used in a wide variety of applications beyond their current scope. The federated approach (developed in SUNRISE) to draw scenarios from connected/affiliated scenario databases allows their data to be accessed and utilized across various platforms, increasing its relevance to stakeholders focused on vehicle validation and automated driving technology development.

2. **Standardization and Industry Alignment.** SYNERGIES aims to utilize standards such as ISO3450X along with standardized scenario definitions and methodologies from projects like SUNRISE, Hi-Drive, V4SAFETY and HEADSTART. This helps to align infrastructure data with industry standards, ensuring that infrastructure data is not only interoperable but also widely accepted by key players in the automotive and regulatory space and bolstering its utility in scenario simulations and validation processes.
3. **Quality Assurance and Scenario Fidelity.** High-quality infrastructure data is highly beneficial for the development of accurate scenarios that reflect real-world driving conditions. By participating in the SYNERGIES project, infrastructure-data providers can help ensure that their data is used to create reliable, high-fidelity scenarios that can test and validate automated driving systems in complex environments, ensuring that systems perform as expected in diverse conditions.
4. **Expansion of Use Cases and Partnerships.** The SYNERGIES platform opens new opportunities for infrastructure-data providers to collaborate with other stakeholders, such as vehicle manufacturers and research organizations. By making their data accessible through a federated scenario database, they can increase their influence in shaping future mobility solutions, expanding their user base and the practical applications of their datasets.

2.3.2 Stakeholder needs

One of the primary needs of the infrastructure-data provider is the establishment of a **common data format**. To ensure the seamless integration and use of their trajectory data, the infrastructure-data provider requires that the SYNERGIES Marketplace defines and enforces a standardized data format. This allows the provider to supply data that is interoperable across different platforms and applications. Without this common standard, the data collected from roadside sensors may not be usable by the broader project, limiting its potential value.

Another important need is the **definition of data quality requirements** by the SYNERGIES Marketplace. The infrastructure-data provider depends on clear specifications regarding what constitutes high-quality data for scenario generation. These requirements must outline the necessary accuracy, resolution, completeness, and timeliness of the data. By having these standards clearly communicated, the infrastructure-data provider can adjust their data collection and processing methods to meet the expectations of other stakeholders, ensuring that the data is fit for use in the project.

Furthermore, the infrastructure-data provider requires **clarity on data quantity expectations** from SYNERGIES Platform Users. The provider needs a well-defined understanding of the volume of data required for different applications, such as scenario simulations and validations. This will enable the infrastructure-data provider to scale their data collection efforts appropriately, ensuring that enough data is available to meet the users' needs without overloading their systems. A lack of clear communication in this regard could result in either insufficient data provision or unnecessary excess.

In addition, the infrastructure-data provider needs **access to feedback from SYNERGIES Platform Users** regarding the usability and relevance of the data provided. This feedback loop is essential for improving the quality of future data collection and refining the data delivery process. By understanding how the data is being used and whether it meets the users' requirements, the infrastructure-data provider can continuously enhance the data provided for scenario generation.

Lastly, the infrastructure-data provider requires **support from the SYNERGIES Marketplace in data handling and storage infrastructure**. Efficient data transfer, storage, and processing mechanisms are necessary to handle large volumes of trajectory data effectively. This infrastructure must be robust and scalable, allowing the provider to deliver data in large batches, depending on the needs of the platform users.

2.3.3 Use Case Diagram

Figure 3 Infrastructure-data provider Use Case diagram

2.4 Euro NCAP

2.4.1 Context

The European New Car Assessment Programme (Euro NCAP) has long been a leader in setting vehicle safety standards through independent testing and widely recognized safety ratings. Euro NCAP's assessments inform consumers and influence manufacturers, fostering a safer automotive industry across Europe. Traditionally focused on crashworthiness, pedestrian protection, and Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS), Euro NCAP now faces the complex task of evaluating Level 3 (L3) automated driving systems, which introduce new safety challenges.

As automated and connected mobility technologies advance, the demands on safety testing are growing more complex. L3 systems require evaluation across diverse driving environments, handling scenarios that extend beyond the scope of conventional testing. This shift necessitates new approaches, such as virtual simulations and hybrid testing, and a platform capable of handling vast scenario variability and data insights.

The SYNERGIES platform offers resources designed to address these needs, providing a Scenario Database that covers diverse traffic interactions, tools for quantifying test coverage, and methods for prioritizing scenarios. Through the platform's capabilities, Euro NCAP can ensure that L3 system assessments are thorough, scientifically grounded, and reflecting real-world conditions.

With these resources, Euro NCAP can continue to ensure that its safety ratings remain relevant, ultimately supporting the safe deployment of automated systems and reinforcing public trust in the evolving landscape of automated and connected mobility.

2.4.2 Stakeholder needs

Real-World Deployment Data Integration

EuroNCAP needs a mechanism supported by SYNERGIES platform to leverage real world data from monitored deployments of automated driving systems. This will enable better understanding of system behaviour, improve safety ratings, and ensure assessments are grounded in live traffic conditions.

Draw Tests from SYNERGIES Scenario Dataspace

EuroNCAP needs the access through SYNERGIES platform to draw relevant test scenarios directly from the scenario databases provided by SYNERGIES partners. This will enable the evaluation of Advanced Driver Assistance Systems and Level 3 automated driving systems using a wide range of realistic and diverse conditions.

Qualification of Scenario Coverage

EuroNCAP needs tools within the SYNERGIES platform to quantify the coverage and relevance of test scenarios. These tools must ensure that the scenarios accurately represent real-world driving conditions, including challenging and safety-critical events, to maintain the robustness and reliability of safety evaluations.

Optimization Scenario Selection

EuroNCAP needs a methodology, supported by SYNERGIES platform, to select a smaller, optimized set of critical test scenarios. This approach should balance comprehensive safety assessments with practical feasibility, ensuring testing processes are focused, efficient, and statistically valid.

SYNERGIES platform shall provide a methodology for selecting a smaller optimized set of scenarios that balance comprehensive safety assessment with feasibility, ensuring that Euro NCAP's testing remains focused, efficient, and statistically valid.

Dynamic Scenario Evolution Tracking

EuroNCAP needs the capability, provided by SYNERGIES platform, to continuously study and adapt test scenarios. This will enable updates to testing protocols in response to evolving traffic patterns, system behaviours and emerging safety challenges, ensuring that safety assessments remain relevant and effective over time.

2.4.3 Use Case Diagram

The Synergies platform shall provide Euro NCAP with diverse, realistic scenarios, coverage evaluation tools, streamlined scenario selection, and insights into real-world performance trends to support rigorous, adaptable L3 system safety assessments.

Figure 4 EuroNCAP Use Case diagram

2.5 Technical Service for type approval

2.5.1 Context

Technical services are responsible for ensuring **regulatory compliance** by making sure that vehicles meet safety and performance standards set by regulatory bodies. The project aims to provide standardized scenarios and methodologies that can simplify compliance with evolving regulations, thereby helping technical services maintain alignment with legal requirements.

Additionally, the implementation of standardized scenarios will ensure **consistency in assessments** across different vehicles and manufacturers, allowing technical services to deliver reliable and comparable results that are critical for their credibility and reputation in the homologation process.

The project's outcomes, such as automated scenario updates and version control, will lead to significant **efficiency improvements** by streamlining the homologation process. This reduction in time and resources required for scenario definition and modification enables technical services to allocate their efforts more effectively, focusing on more complex assessments.

As vehicle technologies evolve, especially in automation and connected systems, technical services must ensure their **adaptation to technological advancements**. The project will equip them with the tools and methodologies necessary to evaluate these new technologies effectively, ensuring they can keep pace with industry changes. Furthermore, by integrating performance metrics tied to regulatory requirements, technical services can enhance their **performance measurement**, allowing for better assessments of Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS) and Automated Driving Systems (ADS). This capability is essential for making informed decisions regarding vehicle safety and homologation.

Technical services can actively participate in the development process through **engagement in development** by providing feedback on scenario definitions, testing methodologies, and regulatory requirements, ensuring that project outcomes align with their operational needs and real-world challenges. Furthermore, the project can include **training and knowledge sharing** through modules or workshops designed for technical service personnel, equipping them with the necessary skills to effectively utilize new tools and methodologies. They will also gain **access to resources** such as a centralized space of federated scenario databases and management system, enabling easy retrieval, modification, and validation of scenarios, thus streamlining their workflow and reducing administrative overhead. The project promotes **collaboration with stakeholders**, including OEMs, regulatory bodies, and research organizations, allowing technical services to gain valuable insights into best practices, emerging trends, and shared challenges in the homologation process. By implementing **best practices**, the project results will provide a clear framework that technical services can follow to improve their processes and ensure adherence to the latest safety standards. Finally, the establishment of **feedback loops** encourages technical services to share their experiences and challenges faced during the implementation of new scenarios or methodologies, allowing for continuous refinement of project outcomes and a more effective homologation process.

2.5.2 Stakeholder needs

Dynamic Scenario Adjustment

Safety regulations evolve over time, often needing updates to existing testing protocols. Technical services need a dynamic platform that allows the adjustment and revalidation of

scenarios to ensure that homologation tests are always conducted according to the most current regulatory frameworks.

Moreover, the testing methodology of scenario definition has changed and there are no specific parameters. For instance, a regulation may define the procedure of merging in the highway and define actors involved but doesn't specify speeds, distances, lane markings, etc. However, technical services need to tailor these scenarios to the ODD definition of the OEMs and define these parameters.

Standardized test scenario formats

Scenario may vary significantly across different databases and platforms from different countries, causing interoperability issues and complicating the integration of scenarios for safety assessments. This can lead to inefficiencies and inconsistencies in testing processes and results. Homologation tests need to be consistent across multiple countries to ensure that safety assessments are standardized and vehicles certified in one country are accepted across the EU. Standardized scenario definitions ensure that homologation tests produce comparable results regardless of location allowing the need of interoperability and recognition between technical services and authorities.

Scenario-Based Performance Metrics for Homologation

Performance metrics in homologation are often derived from general regulatory requirements but are not always linked directly to specific scenarios. The current system lacks standardized, scenario-based metrics that can accurately measure and compare the performance of ADAS and ADS across varied scenarios, making it difficult to ensure consistent safety evaluations. Homologation needs to be based on measurable safety outcomes. By defining performance metrics to scenarios, technical services can assess the effectiveness of ADAS and ADS systems in meeting regulatory safety standards.

Tools

Existing scenario databases typically do not offer advanced filtering capabilities by specific regulatory frameworks or vehicle systems. Users often have to manually select scenarios, which can lead to inefficiencies, incomplete coverage, or misalignment with the appropriate homologation requirements.

Technical services need the ability to filter scenarios based on specific regulatory requirements or system types. This ensures that the relevant scenarios are selected for testing, improving efficiency and alignment with the appropriate homologation criteria.

In addition, defining tests by hand would be a time-consuming activity considering that the new assessment test methodology changes the paradigm of test definition and requires a wide range of scenarios to be tested. Most regulations are open to test different scenarios that should be agreed between the technical service and the homologation applicant. Homologation applicants, test engineers, and homologation engineers often need to review and align on test scenarios. A scenario export tool ensures that all parties work with the same scenarios, streamlining scenario assessment and review across multiple entities.

Suitability of Virtual, track or real-world testing

Testing approaches are often chosen based on availability or convenience rather than scenario suitability. Virtual testing is still emerging, and while real-world and track testing are more established, they are resource-intensive and sometimes impractical for complex or hazardous scenarios, leading to gaps in test coverage and suboptimal use of testing resources.

Some scenarios are more suitable for virtual environments, while others may require track or real-world testing based on resource availability, complexity, or criticality. Technical services need to select the appropriate testing method to ensure efficient and accurate validation.

2.5.3 Use Case Diagram

Figure 5 Technical Servie for type approval Use Case diagram

2.6 Researcher

2.6.1 Context

Researchers act as facilitators of innovation and safety in the scenario-based testing and development of ADAS/AD pre-deployment systems, employing a systematic and analytical approach to reveal the operational boundaries of such systems and to ensure that these complex systems are reliable and safe for their intended use. It is also important to acknowledge that researchers often practice interdisciplinary collaboration where joint work with engineers, software developers, and regulatory bodies is performed to ensure that the testing processes consider technical, legal, and ethical aspects. Their need for scenarios (both realistic and hypothetical ones) and tools for scenarios identification and generation incrementally grows with the number of systems and algorithms under test, while their need to compare results with other researchers on the same scenario pools makes them effective supporters of scenario datasets and scenario manipulation tools' sharing as well as scenario interoperable formats' creation sharing. In validating automated driving systems, a scenario database serves as a crucial resource for researchers and developers. Researchers' possible interaction with the Synergies platform, per identified thematic area is outlined below:

Retrieve test scenarios for XiL testing: The scenario database can be integrated into simulation environments and hardware-in-the-loop systems, allowing for realistic testing of algorithms without the risks associated with on-road testing.

Test Scenario variations: Researchers can use tools for automatic scenario generation in order to obtain new test scenarios for better test objectives coverage.

Synthetic Data Generation from real-world data: Researchers often create simulation environments where they can use annotated data to generate synthetic training scenarios. Hence, tools for synthetic data generation from annotated real data would be used.

Safety & robustness evaluation of AD systems: Researchers use scenarios from the database to test the automated driving system's algorithms and functions. In order to perform SOTIF analysis, (hazardous) scenarios that can lead to system degradation need to be discovered and studied. In addition, evaluating how the system handles rare cases (the long-tail problem) is vital for ensuring robustness.

- **Cross-Validation:** Researchers can cross-reference the outcomes of a SuT with different scenarios in the database to ensure consistency and reliability across multiple tests. This can help confirm that the system can generalize its learning to a variety of driving contexts.
- **Regression Testing:** As updates or modifications are made to the automated driving system, researchers can revisit scenarios from the database to conduct regression testing. This ensures that new changes do not adversely affect existing functionalities.
- **Iterative, complexity-building testing:** As updates or modifications are made to the automated driving system, researchers can create variations of scenarios from the database to increase scenario complexity based on selected parameters (e.g. number of surrounding agents, sources of occlusions etc.).

Training Machine Learning Models: Data produced when different scenarios are executed are needed in order to effectively train and test an AD stack module developed with ML in simulation.

Stakeholder Communication: Researchers can use scenario-based testing results to communicate findings to stakeholders, regulatory bodies, and the public, demonstrating the efficacy and performance limitations of automated driving technologies.

Regulatory Compliance: Curated and approved scenario databases can aid in ensuring that automated systems comply with regulatory frameworks, helping to build confidence in prototypes' deployment in real-world scenarios.

2.6.2 Stakeholder needs

Source data properties, content and viewpoints

- **Time synchronization:** Raw data that include object-level information generated by multiple static and dynamic agents shall be recorded using a common time reference in order to avoid data synchronization issues.
- **Data viewpoints and modalities:** Source data shall include data captured from different viewpoints (vehicle-only, infrastructure-only) and modalities (camera-only, LiDAR-only, camera-LiDAR fusion). The viewpoint and modality information should be recorded in the object-level data as metadata.
- **Support for V2X-enabled systems testing:** Source data shall be rich enough to support V2X simulation, i.e. allow the integration of communication models. This implies that *additional* attributes to facilitate the extraction and generation of scenarios with V2X elements (agents'

connectivity flag, types of connectivity, RSU node characteristics) shall be considered in data collection. Such data from real world settings are difficult to be collected since they require synchronization of multiple agents' recording the same scene and they are indeed missing since C-ITS functions penetration is very low currently and hence Synergies could contribute in such datasets creation. **Annotations:** Quality and level of annotation offered can be important when trying to reproduce real world scenarios in simulation. Object-level, lane-level, surface-level annotations can all be considered.

- **Qualification of object-level data:** Groundtruth trajectory and object-level data extracted from traffic scenes by sensor-equipped vehicles or intelligent Road Side Units (RSUs) is what feeds an AD Perception and Prediction system testing process. Metadata is also very important and shall be distinguished in mandatory and optional fields, offering insights on how data was created (sensor suite details) and if the data can be used for multi-agent testing.

Standardization of scenario formats

Test scenario editing for simulation testing is usually a time-consuming process while different test scenario editing tools from different SW providers are used in co-simulation setups. Use of open and standardized test scenario formats such as ASAM OpenScenario/OpenDrive will promote simulation tools' interoperability and reduce scenario editing times.

Extensions to adopted standardized scenario format to support testing of connectivity aspects

The platform shall include scenarios useful for CP testing in the sense that they include multi-agent scenarios, they cover local areas with occlusions (e.g. urban intersections equipped with an RSU) or bigger areas monitored by RSUs (highway scenarios where V2X notifications are provided). Moreover, since these scenarios might be executed in a driving simulation in parallel with a network simulation, scenarios shall be easily parametrized including connectivity triggering conditions and aspects (e.g. number, position and height of the RSUs). Scenario databases which support collective perception testing in urban environment are sparse, giving the platform an opportunity to fill the existing gaps⁵⁰.

Ease-of-use and support for extensions

A well-noted advantage of the platform would be its ability to provide easy access to scenario management tools and guidelines on how a researcher can substitute a module of the platform with its own (e.g. a different scenario extraction tool). Original tools and tools contributed by the R&D community shall be accessible to all type of registered users, along with accompanying information.

Use of ASAM OpenScenario XML and OpenScenario DSL are recommended. Extensions to these formats might be needed to accommodate triggering conditions stemming from use cases with V2X.

Scenario metadata

Good tagging of the scenarios in the database shall enable retrieval of scenarios with different actors' Behaviours (e.g. darting out agent, occluded agent) and ODD parameters (e.g. road with potholes, night, lack of streetlights etc.). Synthetically generated scenarios that are based on real world data should be tagged as such; this will allow researchers and other stakeholders to prioritize testing their modules with those scenarios first. In the case that the V2X elements are not part of the adopted scenario format, these elements should be included in the metadata fields.

Tools for scenario retrieval, configuration and variations

Scenario retrieval tools shall support searches by ODD, actors' Behaviour and different metadata like source of the scenario.

GUI-supported, visual scenario space creation (flexibility in the number of parameters can be offered) will facilitate non-technical researchers in creating scenario variations (and populate the database with new scenarios).

Tools for unusual scenarios not frequently recorded shall be considered possibly using techniques for AI-based adversarial data generation (peculiar movements of objects or VRUs zig-zag walking).

Tools for scenario extraction from real raw recordings shall consider both the ego-vehicle (dynamic and often with occlusions) point of view and the static infrastructure point of view (e.g. BEV images).

Coverage-driven testing and scenario characterization is very important in safety assessment of AD systems and specific tools are needed in order to optimally explore an immense scenario space for pass/fail outcomes of a specific SuT. For this purpose, tools for scenario variations creation should be able to apply coverage-driven automatic scenario generation methods for interesting scenarios generation for a specific SuT.

Tools' extension/replacement

The platform should provide the capability to a developer/researcher to substitute a module of the platform with its own (e.g. replace an adopted scenario extraction tool with a different one).

2.6.3 Use Case Diagram

Figure 6 Research Use Case Diagram

2.7 DB owners

2.7.1 Context

The Database (DB) owners, in this case, represents the scenario database hosts, which are organizations responsible for collecting, curating, and maintaining scenario data essential for Connected, Cooperative, and Automated Mobility (CCAM) validation. These organizations play a pivotal role in the industry by ensuring that the data they provide is of high quality and meets automotive-grade standards, which are crucial for the development and validation of CCAM systems.

Currently, DB owners face several challenges. While they invest significant resources in standardization efforts and scenario development, they often lack assurance about the broad applicability of their scenarios beyond their immediate users. This uncertainty extends to the acceptance of scenario formats, the representativeness of the data, and the level of scenario coverage required for specific Operational Design Domains (ODDs). Additionally, DB owners are tasked with identifying gaps in representativeness and incorporating new data sources to enhance their scenario datasets.

The SYNERGIES project addresses these challenges by providing an interoperable, federated environment for scenario database management. By integrating data from multiple sources, SYNERGIES fosters standardization, streamlines development cycles, and enhances regulatory compliance. The platform enables DB owners to systematically identify new data sources and evaluate their datasets for gaps in scenario representativeness.

Furthermore, SYNERGIES empowers DB owners with tools for governance, data processing, and scenario identification, helping them scale their databases to include a broader range of use cases and stakeholders. The platform's Scenario Dataspace ensures alignment with Europe's data-sharing strategy while promoting the inclusion of new initiatives. With these capabilities, DB owners can increase the usability, interoperability, and acceptance of their scenarios, ensuring they meet industry expectations and contribute effectively to the validation of CCAM systems.

2.7.2 Stakeholder needs

The DB owner's interest in the SYNERGIES project is driven by several factors:

Scenario Usability and Acceptance

DB owners need assurance that the scenarios they host can be effectively used across various platforms and by diverse stakeholders. This includes ensuring that the data is comprehensive, relevant, and meets established quality standards to enable seamless integration and application in CCAM validation processes. To support this, SYNERGIES should ensure that selected scenarios from various sources are sufficiently representative of the Operational Design Domain (ODD) of the system for which the selection was made. Completeness should also consider the level of detail provided for each scenario in the database, ensuring that critical attributes and metadata are consistently described to support robust analysis and validation.

Accessible and Clear Documentation DB owners require access to documentation that is user-friendly, well-organized, and regularly updated. This documentation should support platform usability and provide guidance on incorporating scenario datasets, ensuring consistent and efficient platform use by all stakeholders.

Secure Connectivity and Data Management

It is essential for DB owners to have mechanisms to securely share, access, and manage data. This includes tools for secure connectivity, privacy protection, and data traceability, ensuring compliance with privacy laws and safeguarding sensitive information.

Secure Cloud Hosting Environment

DB owners need assurance that the platform hosting their scenario data operates in a secure and reliable cloud environment. This includes the need for robust data protection measures, high availability, and compliance with industry security standards. Scalability and resilience are essential to accommodate increasing platform usage over time. Additionally, there is a need for mechanisms that ensure secure data exchange, including the use of secure APIs, encryption protocols, and authentication and authorization processes. To maintain accountability, DB owners require data traceability features that allow for tracking and auditing of changes made to the datasets.

Integration with External Data Sources

DB owners need the ability to integrate external data sources with their existing databases to enhance the range and diversity of scenarios within the scenario database. However, the focus should be on achieving sufficient scenario coverage. This is critical to ensuring that the database effectively supports CCAM validation requirements by encompassing scenarios representative of the Operational Design Domain (ODD).

Gap Analysis and Coverage Improvement

The platform shall provide gap analysis tools that detect areas with insufficient scenario coverage based on defined criteria, suggesting additional scenarios or data sources to improve completeness. This will allow DB owners to identify gaps in scenario datasets, ensuring that the data provided covers a wide range of use cases and is comprehensive for CCAM validation.

2.7.3 Use Case Diagram

Figure 7 DB owner Use Case diagram

2.8 Interoperability needs

2.8.1 Context

Interoperability considerations ensures that assets and systems are not only compatible with each other but also ensure efficient future collaboration and inter-systems integration. That is a crucial aspect of SYNERGIES outcomes:

1. **Collaboration across multiple actors:** ADS conception and validation involves a diverse set of stakeholders including OEM, Tiers X, infrastructure-data providers, technical services, researchers and software solutions providers. Interoperability provides efficient collaboration that leads to higher quality outcomes, minimizing both time and costs in the conception, development and validation stages of systems.
2. **Standardization:** regulatory authorities are pushing for standardization, notably around scenario-based approaches in ADS validation. Interoperability ensures that methods and tools are compliant with emerging standards, improving adoption of these standards and making it easier for stakeholders to meet future regulatory requirements.
3. **Tool and system efficiency:** by ensuring integration between data generation and analysis tools, scenario generation and storage systems, and validation frameworks from several actors, interoperability allows for a cohesive workflow. It ensures that these actors and their systems and tools can communicate and work together, preventing rework and isolated solutions.

2.8.2 Stakeholders needs

In this context, all stakeholders need to interact across a scope that covers the entire range of activities: from the collection of relevant data to the generation of evidence required for ADS validation. This leads to transverse constraints that must be considered in every link of the chain.

Organisational interoperability

This primarily concerns organisational aspects: the information exchanged policy, sharing of responsibilities, roles definition, and permissions must be shared, understandable, and compatible.

Pragmatic interoperability

For exchanges between organizations and systems to be efficient, the exchanged elements and their intended use must be understood and shared. This is accomplished by sharing methods, the origin and intended use of data and systems, and guidance.

Semantic interoperability

Stakeholders must understand each other and must understand what they get from another system: concepts and terms must be shared. This requires the adoption of common glossaries, taxonomies, ontologies, descriptors as frame of references.

Functional interoperability

For components to interact effectively, systems must be designed to facilitate their integration into a tool chain. This includes covering a clear and limited functional scope and providing features that enable seamless integration, such as standard deployment assets, embedded documentation, configuration management or export features.

Technical interoperability

One basis: systems must be designed to be interconnect-able, fostering automation. This requires opening their interface (APIs), using open and preferably standard protocols and formats for inputs and outputs, and ensuring compatibility with systems intended for interconnection (such as a federation layer).

Data interoperability

And finally, information systems interconnection mainly consists of data exchanges. All transversal requirements related to data management must be met by all stakeholders: ensuring traceability, end-to-end security, and enabling configuration management across the entire data lifecycle.

2.8.3 Use Case Diagram

Figure 8 Interoperability Use Case diagram (1)

Figure 9 Interoperability Use Case diagram (2)

2.9 Other stakeholders

2.9.1 Government Agencies

Government agencies are introducing regulations and policies to govern the operation and testing of automated vehicles under specific conditions. For instance, the United Kingdom enacted the [Automated Vehicles \(AV\) Act](#) in 2024 to regulate the use of automated vehicles on roads and other public areas. Similarly, Germany's Autonomous Driving Act, in effect since 2021, permits the operation of level 4 automated vehicles. France's Loi d'Orientation des Mobilités (LOM), established in 2019, facilitates the testing and deployment of autonomous vehicles. These regulations are essential for countries aiming to introduce AVs on public roads, necessitating tools that streamline the processes of authorization, licensing, and operation. By implementing such frameworks, governments ensure the safe integration of automated vehicles into existing transportation systems, addressing both technological advancements and public safety concerns.

Figure 10 Government agencies Use Case diagram

2.9.2 Public Entities

Public entities such as traffic management centres and road operators must ensure safety on urban, interurban, and national roads. They need to manage economic and technical resources wisely, ensuring investments are cost-effective, technologies are up-to-date, and operations are efficient to maximize the benefits of autonomous vehicles (AVs). For instance, the scenarios can help cities identify critical zones where AVs need additional information to operate safely due to poor vertical or horizontal demarcation, bridges, etc. This prioritization of resources, based on the number of devices (e.g. Road Side Units) required to support AVs, can lower installation and maintenance costs. It also aids in infrastructure planning and policy development.

3 LIST OF REQUIREMENTS

Building upon the comprehensive stakeholder needs outlined in Section 2, this section translates those diverse expectations into a structured set of high-level requirements for the SYNERGIES project. These requirements serve as the foundation for developing a robust, interoperable platform that addresses the various needs of stakeholders, ranging from OEMs to technical services, researchers, infrastructure providers, and beyond.

The high-level requirements encapsulated in this section aim to ensure that the SYNERGIES platform delivers value through its capabilities in scenario generation, data management, and system validation.

To provide clarity and structure, the requirements have been categorized into three distinct groups:

- **Requirements for the Scenario Dataspace.** These address the creation, management, and integration of diverse scenario databases to enable seamless access, interoperability, and alignment with the varied needs of stakeholders. Key focuses include ensuring data quality, traceability, and the ability to support complex and evolving validation use cases.
- **Requirements for the Marketplace.** This category outlines the tools and frameworks needed to foster collaboration among stakeholders. It emphasizes features like scenario generation, data exchange, and user interaction, which are critical for supporting ongoing advancements in CCAM technologies.
- **Requirements for the SYNERGIES Platform.** These define the core functionalities and infrastructure necessary for the platform to operate efficiently and scalably. Key considerations include interoperability, modularity, performance, and compliance with industry standards and regulatory requirements.

Each requirement in these categories has been carefully derived to address specific stakeholder challenges, such as interoperability, regulatory compliance, data security, and performance scalability. By aligning with these requirements, the SYNERGIES platform is poised to meet the industry's needs for scenario-based validation while advancing the state-of-the-art in CCAM development.

3.1 Scenario Dataspace Requirements

3.1.1 Req_01 Interoperable Scenario Database Development

- **Title:** Interoperable Scenario Database Development
- **Actors:** Euro NCAP, OEMs, Database Owner, Technical Services
- **State of the art:** Current databases are fragmented, limiting data interoperability and consistency in safety assessments. Lack of shared taxonomies complicates Euro NCAP's ability to compare safety performance across systems.
- **Behaviour:** In SYNERGIES, Euro NCAP shall ensure the development of a standardized database for seamless data sharing, consistent safety protocol implementation, and regular updates. It will include APIs for cross-platform integration and taxonomy standardization for more reliable safety assessments.

- **Rationale:** Euro NCAP requires an interoperable scenario database to ensure uniform ADAS/ADS safety testing, allowing for reliable cross-system comparisons and adherence to safety protocols across stakeholders.

3.1.2 Req_02 Harmonization of Scenario-Based Safety Assessment

- **Title:** Harmonization of Scenario-Based Safety Assessments Across Borders and Jurisdictions.
- **Actors:** Euro NCAP, OEMs, Technical Services, Regulatory Bodies, Database Owners.
- **State of the art:** Differences in national regulations create inconsistencies in applying safety assessments across borders, leading to variations in how ADS and ADAS are validated and accepted despite Euro NCAP's standardized framework.
- **Behaviour:** Synergies will work with Euro NCAP to harmonize scenario-based safety assessments across Europe, aligning scenario selection, testing methods, and safety criteria with both national and international regulations. Scenarios will include jurisdiction-specific variables, such as road signs and traffic rules, while maintaining a standardized framework to ensure consistent testing and validation across borders.
- **Rationale:** Harmonizing scenario-based safety assessments across Europe is essential for ensuring ADS and ADAS meet consistent high standards. Aligning assessments with Euro NCAP's protocols and national regulations will streamline the approval process for automated driving technologies across countries.

3.1.3 Req_03 Comprehensive Scenario Coverage

- **Title:** Comprehensive Scenario Coverage for Varying Road Environments, Edge Cases, and Complex Traffic Scenarios.
- **Actors:** Euro NCAP, OEMs, Database Owner, Technical Services.
- **State of the art:** Current safety assessments often miss rare, high-risk situations and complex interactions involving non-standard vehicles, leading to incomplete validation of automated systems.
- **Behaviour:** Synergies shall develop scenarios across various ODDs, including rare and complex events. Euro NCAP shall validate these scenarios to ensure they meet safety protocols, using real-world data and version control to track updates and maintain compliance with evolving standards.
- **Rationale:** Euro NCAP needs scenarios that reflect real-world complexities (e.g., mixed traffic, public transportation, edge cases) to comprehensively test ADAS/ADS performance in diverse, unpredictable environments.

3.1.4 Req_04 Scenario for Evaluating V2X

- **Title:** Scenario for Evaluating V2X Communication and Cooperation System.
- **Actors:** Euro NCAP, OEMs, Database Owner, Technical Services, Infrastructure Providers, Researchers.
- **State of the art:** Current scenarios for V2X communication lack coverage of critical cooperative elements, such as intersection management and hazard warnings, which are

vital for effective connected mobility systems. This gap impacts the thoroughness of V2X system validation.

- **Behaviour:** Stakeholders will create scenarios that test V2X communication across diverse traffic conditions, focusing on cooperative maneuvers, data-sharing, and real-time decision-making. Euro NCAP will ensure these scenarios meet high safety standards by guiding the development process, emphasizing critical safety outcomes in vehicle dynamics and V2X interactions. The scenarios will also include detailed connectivity aspects, such as viewpoints (vehicle-only, infrastructure-only, cooperative) and sensor modalities (camera, LiDAR, fusion methods).
- **Rationale:** Although Euro NCAP does not lead the development of V2X scenarios, it plays a pivotal role in ensuring these scenarios align with safety protocols. By providing safety frameworks and criteria, Euro NCAP ensures rigorous testing of V2X systems, facilitating the integration of connected technologies to improve road safety and cooperative mobility.

3.1.5 Req_05 Scenario Selection for Virtual Testing

- **Title:** Scenario Selection for Virtual Testing Using Scenario Database.
- **Actors:** Euro NCAP, OEMs, DB owners, Researchers.
- **State of the art:** Euro NCAP is still in the early stages of incorporating virtual testing into its protocols, currently relying mostly on physical testing, which is limited for higher automation levels.
- **Behaviour:** SYNERGIES will help define scenario selection criteria, collaborating with Euro NCAP, OEMs, and technical services. The validated scenario database will cover a range of driving conditions and edge cases for comprehensive ADS/ADAS testing in virtual environments.
- **Rationale:** Virtual testing is crucial to assess the vast number of scenarios needed for higher levels of automation, which is impractical on physical proving grounds. SYNERGIES will support Euro NCAP in building a framework for selecting and validating scenarios from the database to ensure thorough safety assessments.

3.1.6 Req_06 Scenario-Based Validation and Testing

- **Title:** Scenario-Based Validation and Testing.
- **Actors:** Euro NCAP, OEMs, DB owner.
- **State of the art:** Euro NCAP currently relies heavily on physical testing. However, as ADS and ADAS systems grow more complex, a combination of virtual scenario-based testing and physical testing is needed to cover all safety aspect.
- **Behaviour:** SYNERGIES will integrate scenario-based virtual testing with traditional physical testing, enriching Euro NCAP's safety assessments. The testing will include edge cases, mixed traffic, and cooperative V2X scenarios, providing a broader scope for evaluating ADS/ADAS systems.
- **Rationale:** Incorporating virtual scenario-based testing alongside physical testing allows Euro NCAP to evaluate a wider range of safety-critical situations, improving the validation of complex ADS and ADAS systems.

3.1.7 Req_07 Scenario Database-Driven Evidence Dossier

- **Title:** Scenario Database-Driven Evidence Dossier for Testing and Auditing.
- **Actors:** Euro NCAP, OEMs, Database Owner.
- **State of the art:** Currently, OEMs generate evidence dossiers using proprietary methods, often without alignment to Euro NCAP protocols, making consistent validation difficult for high-risk scenarios.
- **Behaviour:** The SYNERGIES Scenario Database should provide OEMs with validated scenarios and methodologies to support the creation of evidence dossiers. These dossiers, based on the database's standardized scenarios, will be audited by Euro NCAP and technical services to ensure proper system performance in scenarios that are impractical to test physically, such as head-on collisions.
- **Rationale:** For scenarios too risky to execute on proving grounds, it is essential to provide OEMs with a structured process to demonstrate ADAS performance through evidence dossiers. These dossiers allow Euro NCAP and technical services to audit safety without requiring physical tests in dangerous conditions.

3.1.8 Req_08 Standardized Data Formats and Interfaces

- **Title:** Standardized Data Formats and Interfaces.
- **Actors:** Platform Users, Data Providers.
- **State of the art:** ASAM Standards, Modelica Association Standards, Khronos Group, ISO, etc.
- **Behaviour:** The platform shall use and contribute to non-discriminatory, publicly accessible standards for the data made available to participants.
- **Rationale:** Facilitate the seamless integration and sharing of content among the platform users, ensuring a consistent and reliable experience.

3.1.9 Req_09 Data Security and Privacy

- **Title:** Data Security and Privacy.
- **Actors:** Platform Users, Data Owners.
- **State of the art:** Selective Privacy/Disclose and zero knowledge proofs, state of the art encryption.
- **Behaviour:** It is RECOMMENDED to explore the use of zero knowledge proofs for the exchange of information in order to protect e.g. sensitive user information. The platform SHOULD build on the principle of Self-Sovereign Identities and data ownership. It is RECOMMENDED to use state of the art encryption for stored data.
- **Rationale:** Ensure the secure storage, access, and management of sensitive data and scenarios.

3.1.10 Req_10 Scenario export format

- **Title:** Scenario export format.

- **Actors:** Platform Users, Data Owners.
- **State of the art:** ASAM OpenSCENARIO XML.
- **Behaviour:** Scenarios made available on the platform SHOULD use the ASAM OpenSCENARIO XML format.
- **Rationale:** The scenario export format shall be standardized and transparent. It shall enable broad use across various companies and institutions. It shall enable the relevant use-cases of the project. It shall be established and tested. It shall have broad support in relevant simulation software.

3.1.11 Req_11 Additional Scenario export formats

- **Title:** Additional Scenario export formats.
- **Actors:** Platform Users, Data Owners.
- **State of the art:** e.g. ASAM Open SCENARIO DSL.
- **Behaviour:** Scenarios made available on the platform MAY be available in additional formats using open specifications.
- **Rationale:** To enable additional applications and use cases, it should be possible to export scenarios in other (open) formats.

3.1.12 Req_12 Consistent interfaces for object and trajectory

- **Title:** Consistent interfaces for object and trajectory data recording.
- **Actors:** Platform Developers, Future Platform Users.
- **State of the art:** ASAM Open Simulation Interface enables recording of trajectories in static and dynamic coordinate frames.
- **Behaviour:** The platform SHALL provide input interfaces to enable consistent processing of input data.
- **Rationale:** A consistent interface (file format) for data recording is required to support the manifold sources of data (recordings from test drives, surveillance cameras, accident data bases). It enables development of consistent data processing algorithms.

3.1.13 Req_13 Standardized, established output format

- **Title:** Standardized, established output format.
- **Actors:** Platform Developers, Future Platform Users.
- **State of the art:** ASAM OpenSCENARIO XML 1.3 has matured over the last years.
- **Behaviour:** The platform SHALL provide scenarios in a standardized, established format.
- **Rationale:** A standardized, established output (scenario) format enables usability of the scenario database.

3.1.14 Req_14 Scenario space designed for homologation use-cases

- **Title:** Representation of a scenario space designed for homologation use-cases.

- **Actors:** Platform Developers, Future Platform Users.
- **State of the art:** N/A.
- **Behaviour:** Scenarios in the SYNERGIES database SHALL form a representative scenario space for homologation. Therefore, they SHALL be discussed with regulators and public access SHALL be granted.
- **Rationale:** The scenarios in the SYNERGIES database shall form a representative scenario space that is designed for one or more homologation use-case(s). Ideally, it is discussed with regulators during the project runtime. In order to serve for homologation use-cases, public access to these scenarios is required.

3.1.15 Req_15 Input data quality

- **Title:** Input data quality.
- **Actors:** Platform Developers, Data Providers, Future Platform Users.
- **State of the art:** Omega Format, etc.
- **Behaviour:** The platform shall provide guidelines about quality requirements for input data (content and accuracy).
- **Rationale:** A minimum quality of input data is required to ensure the proper functionality of tools and methods in the platform. Furthermore, this sets a minimum standard for the output. This enables the platform to ensure a minimum quality for scenarios and improves comparability and searchability for users.

3.1.16 Req_16 Support of scenarios from regulatory institutions

- **Title:** Support of scenarios from regulatory institutions
- **Actors:** OEMs, Tier X Suppliers, Infrastructure Providers, Euro NCAP, Technical Services, Regulatory bodies, Federation layer users
- **State of the art:** ALKS Euro NCAP, NHTSA
- **Behaviour:** The platform should support the access to scenarios from regulatory institutions.
- Regulatory bodies should be able to share their scenarios through the platform.
- **Rationale:** Regulatory institutions provide scenarios within regulatory documents and may maintain their own scenario library in order to provide national / geographic specific situations or scenarios that support traffic rules compliance specific to a country, state boundary or jurisdiction.

3.1.17 Req_17 Sources of scenarios

- **Title:** Sources of scenarios
- **Actors:** OEMs, Tier X Suppliers, Infrastructure Providers, Euro NCAP, Technical Services, Regulatory bodies, Federation layer users
- **State of the art:** DGITM (French Directorate-General for Infrastructure, Transport and the Sea): Generation, feeding and enrichment of scenarios

- **Behaviour:** The SYNERGIES project should ensure to deal with the diversity of scenarios that are required for an ADS validation.
- This includes:
 - nominal scenarios, resulting from system design activities, induced by the intended use (operational design domain, OEDR, route, etc.);
 - Scenarios resulting from accidents, observed in the accidentology representative of the intended use;
 - Scenarios resulting from risk analysis relating to the functional insufficiencies;
 - Scenarios resulting from driving (physical or digital), leading to edge case (rare, unknown and dangerous scenarios) and "Near accidents" or accidents avoided by interaction between driver and users;
 - scenarios specific to priority vehicles and Law Enforcement Officers
- **Rationale:** The validation of a system requires to take into account different sources of scenarios.

3.1.18 Req_18 Traceability, Version Control, and Access Management

- **Title:** Traceability, Version Control, and Access Management of Scenario Database
- **Actors:** OEMs, Technical Services, Euro NCAP, Database Owners, Infrastructure Providers
- **State of the art:** Current systems lack transparent version control and access management, making it difficult to trace scenario evolution and control database access.
- **Behaviour:** Synergies shall implement a robust version control system, documenting all scenario changes over time, and establish access control mechanisms that regulate permissions based on stakeholder roles (e.g., viewing, editing, contributing). This will ensure security, integrity, and traceability of scenarios throughout their lifecycle, supporting audits and regulatory compliance.
- **Rationale:** Maintaining a clear record of scenario usage is essential for auditability, reproducibility, and regulatory compliance, while ensuring secure and appropriate access to the scenario database is critical for protecting data integrity.

3.1.19 Req_19 Dynamic Scenario Adjustment (1)

- **Title:** Dynamic Scenario Adjustment for Evolving Safety Protocols.
- **Actors:** Technical Services, UNECE, EC, Scenario Developers, OEMs, Safety Regulatory Experts.
- **State of the art:** Scenario are normally based on static data that forms predefined scenarios with fixed parameters.
- **Behaviour:** Synergies shall develop a dynamic scenario management system to allow technical services to modify existing scenarios based on safety regulations provisions and save these changes. In addition, the system shall enable automated updates to scenarios when new regulations are published, ensuring that tests are always aligned with the latest safety protocols.

- **Rationale:** Safety regulations evolve over time, often requiring updates to existing scenarios and testing protocols. A dynamic platform that allows technical services to adjust and revalidate scenarios ensures that homologation tests are always conducted according to the most current regulatory frameworks.

3.1.20 Req_20 Dynamic Scenario Adjustment (2)

- **Title:** Dynamic Scenario Adjustment for ODD compliance.
- **Actors:** Technical Services, UNECE, EC, Scenario Developers, OEMs, Safety Regulatory Experts.
- **State of the art:** Scenario are normally based on static data that forms predefined scenarios with fixed parameters.
- **Behaviour:** Synergies shall develop a dynamic scenario management system that allows technical services to retrieve existing scenarios based on the ODD definition. The system must provide the capability to modify specific parameters of these scenarios (e.g., speeds, distances, lane markings) to ensure compliance with OEM-defined ODDs while retaining the integrity of the original scenario.
- **Rationale:** Scenarios must be tailored to the ODD definition of the OEMs. Moreover, the testing methodology of scenario definition has changed and there are no specific parameters. For instance, a regulation may define the procedure of merging in the highway and define actors involved but doesn't specify speeds, distances, lane markings, etc.

3.1.21 Req_21 Standardized Scenario Definition

- **Title:** Standardized Scenario Definition for Cross-Country Homologation.
- **Actors:** Technical Services, UNECE, EC, National Vehicle Safety Authorities, Infrastructure Providers, Scenario Database Owners.
- **State of the art:** Scenario may vary significantly across different databases and platforms from different countries, causing interoperability issues and complicating the integration of scenarios for safety assessments. This can lead to inefficiencies and inconsistencies in testing processes and results.
- **Behaviour:** Compliance history logs should be maintained for each scenario, documenting how each version of the scenario has met previous and current regulatory requirements.
- **Rationale:** Homologation tests need to be consistent across multiple countries to ensure that safety assessments are standardized and vehicles certified in one country are accepted across the EU. Standardized scenario definitions ensure that homologation tests produce comparable results regardless of location.

3.1.22 Req_22 Scenario-Based Performance Metrics for Homologation

- **Title:** Scenario-Based Performance Metrics for Homologation.
- **Actors:** Technical Services, UNECE, EC, OEMs, Performance Analytics Providers, Research Projects.

- **State of the art:** Performance metrics in homologation are often derived from general regulatory requirements but are not always linked directly to specific scenarios. The current system lacks standardized, scenario-based metrics that can accurately measure and compare the performance of ADAS and ADS across varied scenarios, making it difficult to ensure consistent safety evaluations.
- **Behaviour:** The scenario database must include performance metrics that are directly linked to regulatory requirements, ensuring that technical services can measure vehicle performance against UNECE and EC safety standards.

Automated performance evaluation must be integrated, enabling technical services to compare test results against predefined metrics (e.g., braking distance, collision avoidance, lane keeping accuracy).

Each performance metric must have an associated threshold that determines whether the vehicle passes or fails the homologation test, based on regulatory requirements.

- **Rationale:** Homologation must be based on measurable safety outcomes. By defining performance metrics linked to specific scenarios, technical services can assess the effectiveness of ADAS and ADS systems in meeting regulatory safety standards.

3.1.23 Req_23 Scenario filtering by regulation and system

- **Title:** Scenario filtering by regulation and system.
- **Actors:** Technical Services, UNECE, EC, OEMs, Scenario Database Owners.
- **State of the art:** Existing scenario databases typically do not offer advanced filtering capabilities by specific regulatory frameworks or vehicle systems. Users often have to manually select scenarios, which can lead to inefficiencies, incomplete coverage, or misalignment with the appropriate homologation requirements.
- **Behaviour:** Synergies shall integrate advanced filtering capabilities within the scenario database that enable technical services to efficiently filter scenarios by specific regulations and vehicle systems. This feature will ensure that only the relevant scenarios required for homologation tests are displayed, enhancing efficiency and accuracy in the scenario selection process.
- **Rationale:** Technical services need the ability to filter scenarios based on specific regulatory requirements or system types. This ensures that the relevant scenarios are selected for testing, improving efficiency and alignment with the appropriate homologation criteria.

3.1.24 Req_24 Suitability of Virtual, track or real-world testing

- **Title:** Suitability of Virtual, track or real-world testing.
- **Actors:** Technical Services, UNECE, EC, OEMs, Scenario Database Owners, Safety Regulatory Experts.
- **State of the art:** Testing approaches are often chosen based on availability or convenience rather than scenario suitability. Virtual testing is still emerging, and while real-world and track testing are more established, they are resource-intensive and sometimes impractical for complex or hazardous scenarios, leading to gaps in test coverage and suboptimal use of testing resources.

- **Behaviour:** Synergies shall provide a framework to assess the suitability of testing methods (virtual, track, or real-world) for each scenario. This framework must consider factors such as resource availability, scenario criticality, and regulatory requirements to determine the most appropriate testing method.
- **Rationale:** Some scenarios are more suitable for virtual environments, while others may require track or real-world testing based on resource availability, complexity, or criticality. The system should enable technical services to select the appropriate testing method to ensure efficient and accurate validation.

3.1.25 Req_25 Scenario format support for co-simulation

- **Title:** Scenario format support for co-simulation environments
- **Actors:** Researchers, DB Owners, Platform Users, Scenario Database Owners, Future Platform Users, Scenario Developers
- **State of the art:** C-ITS app testing usually requires co-simulation environments combining driving, traffic and network simulations running in parallel.
- **Behaviour:** Source data shall include attributes to facilitate the extraction and generation of scenarios that can support CCAM testing applications. Different viewpoints (vehicle-only, infrastructure-only, cooperative) and modalities (camera-only, LiDAR-only, camera-LiDAR fusion) of source data shall be supported in the Platform.
- **Rationale:** When co-simulation environments are used for testing (e.g. CARLA and network simulation) both environments need to be triggered from the scenario for parallel execution in one simulation run. Such datasets including synchronized vehicular data and infrastructure data are not so many and hence the importance of virtual data generation is big.

3.1.26 Req_26 Raw data content processing and storage

- **Title:** Raw data content processing and storage.
- **Actors:** Researchers, DB Owners, Platform Users, Scenario Database Owners, Future Platform Users, Scenario Developers.
- **State of the art:** NA.
- **Behaviour:** The platform shall allow "raw data" storage and processing to extract new additional scenarios.
 - Note 1: For raw data to be useful for scenario extraction this requires that they have object-level annotations.
 - Note 2: Consideration of raw data coming from different points of views (vehicle centric, drone observer, static observer) are recommended in order to maximize use of available recordings.
 - Note 2: In order to generate V2X testing scenarios in simulation it would be good to also have such source data from real world (i.e. synchronized vehicular and infrastructure data from multiple traffic agents).

- **Rationale:** The type of data stored provided by the Synergies database shall be diverse, including not only scenarios but also selected raw data, processed or fused raw data.

3.1.27 Req_27 Metadata to facilitate scenario retrieval

- **Title:** Metadata to facilitate scenario retrieval (relevance to SuT, ODDs, Actors traffic Behaviours).
- **Actors:** Researchers, DB Owners, Platform Users, Scenario Database Owners, Future Platform Users, Scenario Developers.
- **State of the art:** ASAM already considers tagging in both Openscenario and OpenODD groups.
- **Behaviour:** Synergies should provide tools for easy scenario retrieval based on the relevance of the scenarios to specific SuT (purpose of the scenario when generated), on the inclusion of ODD listed attributes and possibly also on the inclusion of listed traffic road users' behaviours (e.g. person jaywalking, vehicle braking suddenly). A big list of appropriate tags hosting info on both source data and scenario data is recommended.
- **Rationale:** Easy scenario retrieval from Synergies DB would greatly facilitate the research work on different AD V&V tasks.

3.1.28 Req_28 Sensors independent scenarios

- **Title:** Sensors independent scenarios.
- **Actors:** OEM, Data owner, homologation, standardization.
- **State of the art:** NA.
- **Behaviour:** Does Synergies platform able to deliver a way to be sensor independent?
- **Rationale:** Many data are very dependent of the used sensors. the delivery of the characteristics of the sensors data can be a way to assure the retrospectivity and the interoperability of the data in cross OEM process.

3.1.29 Req_29 Adapted to local regulation

- **Title:** Adapted to local regulation
- **Actors:** OEM, Data owner, homologation, standardization
- **State of the art:** NA.
- **Behaviour:** Synergies platform can be customized depending on the deployment area
- **Rationale:** The scenario selection needs to be tailored to the local regulations.

3.1.30 Req_30 AI act compliance + GDPR

- **Title:** AI act compliance + GDPR
- **Actors:** OEM, Data owner, homologation, standardization
- **State of the art:** NA.
- **Behaviour:** Synergies platform needs to assess the compliance of AI for each scenario

- **Rationale:** The choice and usage of AI models need to follow regulatory guidelines.

3.2 Marketplace Requirements

3.2.1 Req_31 AI Tools for adversarial scenario generation.

- **Title:** AI Tools for adversarial scenario generation.
- **Actors:** Researchers, DB Owners, Platform Users, Scenario Database Owners, Future Platform Users, Scenario Developers.
- **State of the art:** NA.
- **Behaviour:** Generative AI based tools that consider adversarial data generation could be provided by Synergies (peculiar movements of objects or VRUs zig-zag walking).
- **Rationale:** AI is good in generating adversarial data which could then be used for new scenarios which are not occurring so often.

3.2.2 Req_32 Guidelines for ground truth generation

- **Title:** Guidelines for ground truth generation.
- **Actors:** OEM, Data owner, homologation, standardization.
- **State of the art:** NA.
- **Behaviour:** for real dataset, the existing, quality and openness of the ground truth can be essential for testing and training.
- **Rationale:** For real data (not simulated), the existing of data ground truth is essential. the quality of the data ground truth is to be monitored carefully.

3.2.3 Req_33 Identification of critical zones

- **Title:** Identification of critical zones where AVs require support from additional sensors.
- **Actors:** Public entities, OEMs, Technical Services, Infrastructure Providers, Services providers.
- **State of the art:** Public entities install roadside units and additional sensors to aggregate information, improving efficiency and safety. Vehicle-to-everything (V2X) technologies are used to exchange information with connected and automated vehicles. However, identifying and prioritizing the specific locations for installing these devices has been challenging. This difficulty reduces their benefits and increases installation and maintenance costs.
- **Behaviour:** Public entities and stakeholders use the platform to recreate scenarios to analyse the effects caused by the installation of roadside units in areas where AVs require additional information. A summary report is expected containing information about the data used, as well as critical indicators.
- **Rationale:** Public entities use the platform to recreate scenarios to analyse the effects caused by the installation of road infrastructure sensors (i.e., roadside units) in areas where AVs could require additional information to operate safely or to limit AVs Operation to specific speed limits for example. A summary report is expected containing

information about the data used, as well as critical indicators. This solution fills ODDs issues from the perspective of public entities.

3.2.4 Req_34 Scenario Export tool

- **Title:** Scenario Export tool.
- **Actors:** Technical Services, UNECE, EC, OEMs.
- **State of the art:** Defining these tests by hand would be a time-consuming activity considering that the new test methodology changes the paradigm of test definition and requires a wide range of scenarios to be tested.
- **Behaviour:** Synergies shall develop a scenario export tool that allows technical services to select scenarios from the database for assessment. This tool must facilitate the export of chosen scenarios in a standardized format, ensuring that all necessary parameters and metadata are included for easy review by homologation engineers and test engineers.
- **Rationale:** Most regulations are open to test different scenarios that should be agreed between the technical service and the homologation applicant. Homologation applicants, test engineers, and homologation engineers often need to review and align on test scenarios. A standardized scenario export tool ensures that all parties work with the same data, streamlining scenario assessment and review across multiple entities.

3.3 SYNERGIES Platform Requirements

3.3.1 Req_35 Open-Source or Open-Access License

- **Title:** Open-Source or Open-Access License.
- **Actors:** Platform Participants.
- **State of the art:** Open-Source licenses.
- **Behaviour:** The platform shall use open source or open-access licenses for specifications and documents.
- **Rationale:** Ensure all participants can safely use the specifications and data without legal concern.

3.3.2 Req_36 Interoperability and Compatibility

- **Title:** Interoperability and Compatibility.
- **Actors:** Platform Users, Existing Industry Tools/Frameworks.
- **State of the art:** EDC Data Spaces, GaiaX, etc.
- **Behaviour:** It is RECOMMENDED to re-use and contribute to existing open-source frameworks, software and libraries.
- **Rationale:** Allow seamless integration and exchange of data and scenarios between the platform and other relevant systems.

3.3.3 Req_37 Scalability and Performance

- **Title:** Scalability and Performance.
- **Actors:** Platform Operators, Future Platform Users.
- **State of the art:** Serverless architectures.
- **Behaviour:** The platform SHOULD facilitate cloud-based solutions for the deployments that allow the scaling of the application with a growing number of users.
- **Rationale:** Enable the platform to accommodate the evolving needs of the automotive industry and the growing demand for test scenario management.

3.3.4 Req_38 Extensibility and Modularity

- **Title:** Extensibility and Modularity.
- **Actors:** Platform Developers, Future Platform Users.
- **State of the art:** Modular simulation architectures, clear interfaces, separation of concerns.
- **Behaviour:** The platform SHALL be developed in a modular way focusing on the clear separation of concerns with open specifications for interfaces in order to allow the integration of solutions from the stakeholder community.
- **Rationale:** Enable the easy integration of new features, components, and functionalities over time, including support for emerging standards and technologies.

3.3.5 Req_39 Versioning and Change Management

- **Title:** Versioning and Change Management.
- **Actors:** Platform Users, Content Curators.
- **State of the art:** GitHub/Gitlab, Sematic Versioning, decentralized databases.
- **Behaviour:** The platform SHALL use state of the art technology to track changes of the platform software and its content to ensure the integrity and traceability of changes.
- **Rationale:** Provide a reliable and transparent mechanism for tracking changes, managing updates, and ensuring the integrity of the platform's content over time.

3.3.6 Req_40 Reporting and Analytics

- **Title:** Reporting and Analytics.
- **Actors:** Platform Users, Platform Operators.
- **State of the art:** AWS/Azure Dashboards and Frameworks
- **Behaviour:** It is RECOMMENDED to track important events and associated key performance indicators (KPIs).
- **Rationale:** Enable data-driven decision-making, performance monitoring, and continuous improvement of the platform and its usage.

3.3.7 Req_41 Required Standards

- **Title:** Required Standards.
- **Actors:** Platform Developers.
- **State of the art:** NA.
- **Behaviour:** Standards necessary to fulfil the synergies use cases shall be listed separately in the requirements document.
- **Rationale:** Dependencies necessary to fulfil the use cases defined in the SYNERGIES project need to be transparently documented in the requirements list for developers to estimate implementation efforts.

3.3.8 Req_42 Communication between users and data providers

- **Title:** Communication between users and data providers.
- **Actors:** Platform Developers, Data Providers, Future Platform Users.
- **State of the art:** NA.
- **Behaviour:** The platform shall enable users to communicate requirements and provide feedback directly to data providers regarding the quality and content of their data.
- **Rationale:** Providing users with the ability to communicate requirements and feedback directly to data providers ensures that the data meets users' specific needs and quality standards. This feedback loop fosters transparency, helps data providers improve their offerings, and enhances user satisfaction.

3.3.9 Req_43 Federated architecture

- **Title:** Federated architecture.
- **Actors:** Platform Developers, Data Providers.
- **State of the art:** Federated architecture.
- **Behaviour:** The platform should implement a federation layer that provides a unified view of data from disparate sources without requiring physical data movement or consolidation.
- **Rationale:** Multiple actors may maintain and be the owner of their own scenario database (Safety pool, ADSCENE, Streetwise, L3-pilot, Hi-Drive, ...).
- The objective of the SYNERGIES platform is to provide an access to external existing databases in a standardized way to allow users to access scenario catalogues of third parties using a single system endpoint.

3.3.10 Req_44 Intended users

- **Title:** Intended users
- **Actors:** Future Platform Users
- **State of the art:** NA.
- **Behaviour:** Within the SYNERGIES project, it is required to consider the specific needs of several actors: system designer, transport operator, local authority in charge of transport

(city council, regional transport agency), third party assessor (OQA - Approved & Qualified Organisms), authorities' bodies.

- **Rationale:** Scenarios are useful for several actors and activities in the context of development, training, virtual testing and validation of ADS systems.

3.3.11 Req_45 In-Service Monitoring and Reporting (ISMR)

- **Title:** In-Service Monitoring and Reporting (ISMR) Scenarios.
- **Actors:** OEMs, Database Owners, Technical Services, Euro NCAP.
- **State of the art:** Currently, data is not systematically integrated into scenario databases for ADS testing.
- **Behaviour:** Synergies shall develop scenarios from ISMR reports, focusing on edge cases and specific situations that led to vehicle failures. Scenarios should incorporate the causes of incidents and help assess system robustness.
- **Rationale:** Use data to generate scenarios based on real-world incidents for continuous improvement in ADS and ADAS testing.

3.3.12 Req_46 Detection of similar scenarios

- **Title:** Detection of similar scenarios.
- **Actors:** Probably Technical Services and Database Owners.
- **State of the art:** NA.
- **Behaviour:** The platform shall be able to detect similarities in scenarios
- **Rationale:** ensure that scenarios do not duplicate or overlap, avoid duplicated work/storage

3.3.13 Req_47 Assurance of Scenario Usability and Acceptance

- **Title:** Assurance of Scenario Usability and Acceptance.
- **Actors:** DB Owners, OEMs, Tier X Suppliers, Euro NCAP, Technical Services, Legal Experts, Regulatory Authorities.
- **State of the art:** NA.
- **Behaviour:** The SYNERGIES platform shall establish criteria for scenario quality, completeness, and representativeness. It will also provide validation mechanisms to ensure that scenarios meet automotive-grade and regulatory standards.
- **Rationale:** Ensures that scenarios provided by DB owners are compliant with industry standards (Such as ASAM OpenScenario and OpenDrive) and accepted by authorities, which increases the scenarios' applicability.

3.3.14 Req_48 User Documentation for Platform End-Users

- **Title:** User Documentation for Platform End-Users.
- **Actors:** DB Owners, Platform Users, Platform Developers, Platform Administrators, Data Providers.

- **State of the art:** NA.
- **Behaviour:** The platform shall provide a user-friendly, web-based documentation system (e.g., Wikis, knowledge bases) accessible to all users. It will include guides for common tasks, role-based instructions, troubleshooting tips, and references to standards. It should also be updated regularly to reflect changes in the platform.
- **Rationale:** Providing clear documentation ensures that users can effectively navigate and utilize the platform's features, promoting adoption, ease of use, and operational efficiency.

3.3.15 Req_49 Secure Connectivity and Data Management

- **Title:** Secure Connectivity and Data Management.
- **Actors:** DB Owners, Platform Users, Stakeholders (OEMs, Tier X, Infrastructure Providers).
- **State of the art:** NA.
- **Behaviour:** The platform shall include an automated feedback and survey tool to collect insights and requests from all stakeholders (OEMs, Tier X, suppliers, infrastructure providers). This data will be reviewed during regular development cycles.
- **Rationale:** Regular feedback loops with stakeholders ensure that the platform evolves in alignment with their changing needs and expectations.

3.3.16 Req_50 Compliance with National and International Privacy Laws

- **Title:** Compliance with National and International Privacy Laws.
- **Actors:** Platform Users, DB Owners, Platform Administrators, Regulatory Bodies.
- **State of the art:** NA.
- **Behaviour:** The platform shall enforce strict compliance with national and international privacy laws (e.g., GDPR, CCPA). Raw personal data shall be anonymized by default, and data processing shall require explicit consent. Users shall have the ability to access, edit, or delete their personal data in accordance with legal requirements.
- **Rationale:** Ensures a secure, reliable method for DB owners to connect to the SYNERGIES platform, manage their data, and make updates without compromising data integrity or security.

3.3.17 Req_51 Secure Cloud Hosting

- **Title:** Secure Cloud Hosting.
- **Actors:** Platform Users, Platform Operators, DB Owners.
- **State of the art:** NA.
- **Behaviour:** The platform shall implement secure APIs and encryption protocols for data exchange, with authentication and authorization mechanisms to ensure only verified users can access or modify the data. Data traceability shall be maintained to track changes.

- **Rationale:** Hosting the platform in a secure cloud environment ensures data protection, availability, and compliance with industry security standards. It also allows for scalability and resilience in handling increasing platform usage.

3.3.18 Req_52 Integration with External Data Sources

- **Title:** Integration with External Data Sources.
- **Actors:** DB Owners, Platform Operators.
- **State of the art:** Currently, scenario databases are limited by the data sources they can access, which affects the variety and representativeness of the scenario data.
- **Behaviour:** The platform shall support the integration of external data sources, enabling DB owners to import data from various providers and incorporate it into their scenario datasets, ensuring comprehensive data coverage.
- **Rationale:** Allowing DB owners to integrate external data sources enhances the completeness and diversity of scenario datasets, leading to more comprehensive validation coverage.

3.3.19 Req_53 Gap Analysis and Coverage Improvement

- **Title:** Gap Analysis and Coverage Improvement.
- **Actors:** DB Owners, SYNERGIES Platform.
- **State of the art:** NA.
- **Behaviour:** The platform shall provide gap analysis tools that detect areas with insufficient scenario coverage based on defined criteria, suggesting additional scenarios or data sources to improve completeness.
- **Rationale:** Allows DB owners to identify gaps in scenario datasets, ensuring that the data provided covers a wide range of use cases and is comprehensive for CCAM validation.

3.3.20 Req_54 Open API

- **Title:** Deliver Open API to access different data or scenario generator.
- **Actors:** OEM, Data owner, homologation, standardization.
- **State of the art:** NA.
- **Behaviour:** Synergies platform should deliver a way to access different format of data to assure usability and interoperability of the different database
- **Rationale:** open data is a key ingredient. one way to assure openness is to deliver an open API that deliver access to the data regardless of the standard format.

3.3.21 Req_55 Open and detailed Guidelines for data tagging

- **Title:** Open and detailed Guidelines for data tagging.
- **Actors:** OEM, Data owner, homologation, standardization.
- **State of the art:** NA.

- **Behaviour:** Synergies platform should assure minimum tagging set and a convenient guideline for tag generation
- **Rationale:** Scenario extraction easiness is based essentially on the quality of the data tags. Manual or AI based tagging both methods need to deliver standard and exhaustive methodology.

3.3.22 Req_56 Reports to evaluate the effects of regulations and policies

- **Title:** Reports to evaluate the effects of regulations and policies for defined CCAM scenarios.
- **Actors:** Government Agencies, OEMs, Technical Services, Infrastructure Providers, Services providers.
- **State of the art:** Government agencies are regulating autonomous vehicle operations:
 - 2024 UK: Automated Vehicles (AV) Act.
 - 2021 Germany: Autonomous Driving Act.
 - 2019 France: Loi d'Orientation des Mobilités (LOM).
- **Behaviour:** Government agencies and stakeholders recreate scenarios where a specific regulation can be applicable to evaluate its effects or impacts. Possible modifications can be suggested at the end of the evaluation, and a summary report is expected containing information about the data used, as well as critical indicators.
- **Rationale:** Government agencies in countries such as the UK, Germany, and France are regulating autonomous vehicle operations. Tendency that will be followed by other countries because of the need of clear rules. The platform has the potential to facilitate the evaluation of the impact of these regulations on CCAM scenarios.

3.3.23 Req_57 User Access and Permissions

- **Title:** User Access and Permissions
- **Actors:** Platform Users, Platform Administrators
- **State of the art:** AWS IAM, Single-Sign-On, OIDC
- **Behaviour:** The platform SHOULD use the open id connect (OIDC) standards to manage access to apps and resources.
- **Rationale:** Ensure appropriate access control and role-based permissions to manage user privileges and content visibility.

3.3.24 Req_58 Community Engagement and Collaboration

- **Title:** Community Engagement and Collaboration
- **Actors:** Platform Users, Stakeholder Community
- **State of the art:** EDC Data Spaces, GaiaX, etc
- **Behaviour:** It is RECOMMENDED to re-use and contribute to existing open-source frameworks, software and libraries.

- **Rationale:** Allow seamless integration and exchange of data and scenarios between the platform and other relevant systems

3.3.25 Req_59 Metadata to facilitate scenario retrieval

- **Title:** Metadata to facilitate scenario retrieval (relevance to SuT, ODDs, Actors traffic Behaviour)
- **Actors:** Researchers, DB Owners, Platform Users, Scenario Database Owners, Future Platform Users, Scenario Developers
- **State of the art:** ASAM already considers tagging in both Openscenario and OpenODD groups
- **Behaviour:** Synergies should provide tools for easy scenario retrieval based on the relevance of the scenarios to specific SuT (purpose of the scenario when generated), on the inclusion of ODD listed attributes and possibly also on the inclusion of listed traffic road users' Behaviours (e.g. person jaywalking, vehicle braking suddenly). A big list of appropriate tags hosting info on both source data and scenario data is recommended.
- **Rationale:** Easy scenario retrieval from Synergies DB would greatly facilitate the research work on different AD V&V tasks.

3.3.26 Req_60 Government Agencies

- **Title:** Reports to evaluate the effects of regulations and policies for defined CCAM scenarios
- **Actors:** Government Agencies, OEMs, Technical Services, Infrastructure Providers, Services providers
- **State of the art:** Government agencies define the regulations under which AVs operate. Regulations having an impact on public and private entities. However, as is the case with new technologies, regulations cover specific or studied situations, and adaptations to the existing ones can be needed until the full commercialization of AVs arrives.
- **Behaviour:** Actors recreate scenarios where a specific regulation can be applicable to evaluate its effects or impacts. Possible modifications can be suggested at the end of the evaluation, and a summary report is expected containing information about the data used, as well as critical indicators.
- **Rationale:** Government agencies in countries such as the UK, Germany, and France are regulating autonomous vehicle operations. Tendency that will be followed by other countries because of the need of clear rules. The platform has the potential to facilitate the evaluation of the impact of these regulations on CCAM scenarios.

3.3.27 Req_61 Public Entities

- **Title:** Identification of critical zones where AVs required support from additional sensors
- **Actors:** Public entities, OEMs, Technical Services, Infrastructure Providers, Services providers
- **State of the art:** Public entities install roadside units and additional sensors to aggregate information, with the aim to use the information to improve efficiency and safety. Vehicle-to-everything (V2X) technologies are used to exchange information with connected and

automated vehicles. However, identifying and prioritizing the specific locations for installing these devices has been challenging. This difficulty reduces their benefits and increases installation and maintenance costs.

- **Behaviour:** Actors use the platform to recreate scenarios to analyze the effects caused by the installation of roadside units in areas where AVs require additional information. A summary report is expected containing information about the data used, as well as critical indicators.
- **Rationale:** Public entities use the platform to recreate scenarios to analyse the effects caused by the installation of road infrastructure sensors (i.e., roadside units) in areas where AVs could require additional information to operate safely or to limit AVs Operation to specific speed limits for example. A summary report is expected containing information about the data used, as well as criticality indicators.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable has outlined the diverse needs of stakeholders and presented a comprehensive list of requirements that will guide the project's development. Several key conclusions can be drawn from this analysis:

1. **Unified Access to Scenario Dataspace:** The project's primary objective of providing unified access to a European scenario dataspace through a federated approach addresses a critical need in the CCAM ecosystem. This approach will enable more efficient and comprehensive testing of automated driving systems by leveraging existing resources across various databases.
2. **Diverse Stakeholder Needs:** The requirements gathered from different stakeholders, including OEMs, Tier X suppliers, researchers, infrastructure data providers, Euro NCAP, technical services, and database owners, highlight the complexity of the CCAM validation process. The SYNERGIES platform must be flexible and robust enough to meet these varied needs.
3. **Interoperability and Standardization:** A recurring theme across stakeholder requirements is the need for interoperability and standardization. The SYNERGIES project has the potential to drive industry-wide standards for scenario formats, data quality, and testing methodologies.
4. **AI and Automation:** The incorporation of AI-powered tools for scenario extraction and analysis will significantly enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of CCAM validation processes. This aligns with the industry's move towards more automated and data-driven approaches.
5. **Regulatory Compliance and Safety:** The requirements emphasize the importance of aligning the SYNERGIES platform with regulatory frameworks and safety standards. This will be crucial for the acceptance and adoption of the platform by regulatory bodies and industry stakeholders.
6. **Marketplace Development:** The establishment of a marketplace for scenario generation and analysis tools will foster innovation and collaboration within the CCAM community. This ecosystem approach will be vital for the long-term sustainability and relevance of the SYNERGIES platform.
7. **Data Security and Privacy:** Given the sensitive nature of some of the data involved, the requirements around data security, privacy, and access control are of paramount importance. The SYNERGIES platform must implement robust measures to address these concerns.
8. **Scalability and Future-Proofing:** The requirements indicate a need for a scalable and adaptable platform that can evolve with the rapidly changing CCAM landscape. This forward-looking approach will be essential for the long-term success of the project.

This deliverable serves as a crucial foundation for the subsequent tasks within Work Package 2 and the broader SYNERGIES project. The comprehensive list of requirements will guide the development of concrete technical specifications and the implementation of the federated scenario dataspace and associated tools.

Moving forward, the project team will need to prioritize these requirements, address potential conflicts, and develop a roadmap for implementation. Regular engagement with stakeholders will be essential to ensure that the evolving SYNERGIES platform continues to meet the needs of the CCAM community.

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A. ABBREVIATIONS AND DEFINITIONS

Term	Definition
ADAS	Advanced Driver Assistance Systems
ADS	Automated Driving System
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ALKS	Automated Lane Keeping Systems
API	Application Programming Interface
CCAM	Cooperative, Connected, and Automated Mobility
CCPA	California Consumer Privacy Act
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems
DB	Database
EC	European Commission
Euro NCAP	European New Car Assessment Programme
HMI	Human-Machine Interface
IAM	Identity and Access Management
IoT	Internet of Things
ISMR	In-Service Monitoring and Reporting
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ODD	Operational Design Domain
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
RSS	Responsibility-Sensitive Safety
SAE	Society of Automotive Engineers
SuT	System under Test
UNECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe
V2X	Vehicle-to-Everything